

Carbon Nanotubes and Graphene Nanoplatelets in Epoxy Composite: Dispersion and Synergy Effect

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Aim

- Composites have excellent mechanical-to-weight ratio properties but exhibit poor electrical properties due to the presence of dielectric polymer.
- Integration of carbon-based nanofillers such as carbon black (CB), carbon nanotubes (CNT) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) into polymer resin can improve the electrical performance.
- Combination of different types of nanofillers can result in synergistic effect that can further improve the electrical properties.

Aim

- The aim of the project is to develop conductive epoxy resin composites by integration of carbon nanotubes and graphene nanoplatelets.

Objectives

- To investigate the electrical and rheological properties of nano-modified epoxy composites.
- To study the synergistic effect of using hybrid nanofillers in epoxy composites.

Materials and Methodology

Figure 1 SEM images of CNT carpets.

Figure 2 Dispersion process using Silverson L5M model shear mixer.

Figure 3 Dispersion quality before (left image) and after (right image) of modified suspension.

- Highly aligned carpets of CNT with approximate length of 1 mm was used as one of the nanofillers.
- Modified suspensions were shear mixed at 1000 RPM for 40 mins at room temperature.

- Optical imaging shows homogenous distribution of nanofillers in polymer resin after mixing.
- Through thickness electrical resistance of cured samples was measured to investigate the bulk electrical conductivity.

Figure 4 Electrical resistance measurement using a multimeter.

Results and Discussion

(a) CNT-modified epoxy composites

- All electrical conductivities of cured samples are within EMI shielding range.
- Only slight electrical improvement as CNT loading concentration increases.

Figure 5 Electrical conductivity of CNT modified epoxy composites at different loading concentration.

(b) Hybrid-modified epoxy composites

- Modest synergistic effect – peak at 0.05 wt% GNP.
- Maximum of 6x improvement in electrical conductivity with addition of GNP.

Figure 7 Electrical conductivity of hybrid modified epoxy composites at different GNP loading concentration.

- 10-fold increase in low shear rate viscosity for 0.1wt% CNT.
- Progressive enhancement in low shear rate viscosity as CNT weight fraction increases.

Figure 6 Viscosity of various loading concentration of CNT modified epoxy suspension at 40°.

- Exhibit similar rheological behaviour with CNT modified.

Table 1 Comparison between CNT and hybrid modified samples.

Sample	Viscosity at 1/s (Pa.s)	E. Conductivity (S/m)
0.2wt% CNT only epoxy composite	8.509	0.099
Hybrid (0.2wt% CNT + 0.05wt% GNP) epoxy composite	12.310	0.516

Conclusion

- Only low level of CNT weight fraction of up to 0.2wt% can be used - best compromise between electrical conductivity and processability.
- Slight synergistic effect is obtained with addition of GNP into CNT-only suspension.
- Hybrid modified suspension can further enhance the electrical performance without affecting the viscosity.